

Analysis of Tramadol and Dexamethasone as an Adjuvant to BupivacaineNilesh Dhanwant Sarvaiya¹, Suket Gandhi²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Dahanu Palghar.²M.D. (Anaesthesia), FCCCM (Critical Care Medicine), CIH (Industrial Health), Assistant Professor, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Palghar (Maharashtra)

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Suket Gandhi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: It is necessary to reduce unbearable pain after surgery. Bupivacaine was used as an anaesthetic but recently scientists are cultivating the use of Tramadol and Dexamethasone with Bupivacaine as an effective adjuvant to increase the potentiality of Bupivacaine. Tramadol has been used for the reduction of the unbearable pain after surgery while dexamethasone has been used for the cure of the inflammation caused after operative measure. The study provides different other ways for reducing pain and the patients tendency to request for analgesics.

Aims and Objective: To compare the post-operative analgesic efficacy of tramadol and dexamethasone as an adjuvant to bupivacaine.

Method: The observational study was carried out in India among 120 randomly selected patients into 3 groups, considering different inclusion and exclusion criteria with proper written consent of the patients. 20-30 age group patients should be allowed with orthopedic surgery in the upper limb. Different tests like ANOVA, paired t test, chi square tests etc were carried out for maintaining statistical significance.

Result: Group I (tramadol) had a sensory response mean of 10.85 (SD 3.05) and motor response mean of 21.83 (SD 4.55). Group II (Dexamethasone) had a sensory response mean of 10 (SD 2.12) and motor response mean of 15.14 (SD 4.25). Group III showed sensory and motor response means of 21.25 (SD 6.25) and 28.19 (SD 4.45), respectively. Group II's sensory block mean duration was 420.65 minutes (p=0.0355), and motor block mean was 356 minutes (p=0.0498). Analgesic dose timing in Group II averaged 655.36 minutes (p=0.0335).

Conclusion: Dexamethasone significantly better sensory and motor responses, as well as more favorable durations for sensory and motor blocks.

Keywords: Dexamethasone, Tramadol, Bupivacaine, Post-Operative Pain.

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Introduction

Pain management is crucial to medical care, particularly in surgical and postoperative circumstances. Effective pain control promotes patient comfort, assists rapid recovery, reduces hospital stays, and significantly minimizes the chance of chronic pain development [1]. Local anaesthetics, such as Bupivacaine (C₁₈H₂₈N₂O), are commonly used for pain management during and after surgical procedures. Bupivacaine (1-butyl-2', 6'- pipercoloxylidide) belongs to the amide group of local anaesthetics, which are characterized by their chemical stability and longer duration of action compared to ester-based anaesthetics. Ekenstam, a Scandinavian chemist in 1957 synthesized Bupivacaine for the first time, and later in 1963 was introduced into clinics [2]. Bupivacaine is a long-acting local anaesthetic that is extensively used for regional anaesthesia and pain control. It works by blocking sodium channels in the nerve cells, thereby preventing the transmission of nerve impulses. This

blockade of nerve signals results in a loss of perception in the area where the drug is administered. The high solubility of Bupivacaine allows it to penetrate nerve membranes more effectively, contributing to its potency and efficiency compared to other local anaesthetics [3]. Despite its common use and efficacy, the primary challenge with Bupivacaine is it often falls short in its duration of action, which necessitates repeated doses or additional therapies to reduce toxicity and sustain pain relief over extended periods [4]. To solve this restriction, researchers and physicians are exploring the use of adjuvants that can complement Bupivacaine to improve its effectiveness and prolong its activity [5]. Furthermore, in addition to reducing the local anaesthesia dose and supplemental opioids, the use of the adjuvants can lead to faster onset, more complete anaesthesia, and longer-lasting pain relief. Among various putative

adjuvants, Tramadol and Dexamethasone have shown promise in clinical studies [6].

Tramadol is an opioid analgesic that is notable in its dual mode of action. It not only binds to opioid receptors in the brain to reduce pain but also inhibits the absorption of neurotransmitters like serotonin and norepinephrine, which further contributes to its analgesic effects [7]. When used as an adjuvant to Bupivacaine, Tramadol can potentially enhance the pain-relieving qualities of Bupivacaine and lengthen the duration of its action. This combination may give a more effective and longer-lasting pain management approach, lowering the need for frequent dosing and eliminating potential adverse effects associated with larger doses of local anaesthetics [8–11].

Dexamethasone is a potent anti-inflammatory corticosteroid [12]. It is widely used to decrease inflammation and suppress the immunological response in numerous medical diseases [13]. As an adjuvant to Bupivacaine, Dexamethasone can aid in prolonging the duration of anaesthesia by lowering inflammation and suppressing the production of inflammatory mediators that contribute to pain. Additionally, Dexamethasone may help to decrease postoperative nausea and vomiting, which are frequent side effects of anaesthesia and surgery [14,15].

By analysing the potential advantages of Tramadol and Dexamethasone as adjuvants, through this study we look forward to addressing the issue of short duration of effect of Bupivacaine when taken alone for pain management. This will contribute to establishing a more effective and longer-lasting pain management strategy. Furthermore, this might lead to improved patient outcomes, reduced dependence on various analgesics, and a more efficient use of healthcare resources. We believe that the findings from this study will improve the traditional pain management regimens and increase the quality of therapy for patients having surgery.

Materials and Method

Research Design: This is a prospective and interventional study of comparing the utilization of tramadol or dexamethasone, in using them as an adjuvant to bupivacaine. The study was conducted from February 2023 to January 2024 in a multispecialty hospital of India. This randomized study was done with total 120 patients, those who were selected on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria and were divided into 3 groups, each containing 40 patients, named as Group I, Group II, and Group III. Patients of each group were given a specific concentration of both, tramadol and dexamethasone with bupivacaine and also saline with bupivacaine was also tested with another group for the control one. 25ml, 0.5% of bupivacaine was given to the group I patients along with tramadol, 100 mg which is 50mg/ml. Same 25

ml, 0.5% of bupivacaine was given to group II patients along with dexamethasone, 10 mg, which is 4mg/ml. in case of group III, also same 25 ml, 0.5% of bupivacaine was given to patients along with normal saline which was added around 5ml. Three types of sensory block was felt, in first type, a sharp pin type was felt. The second type was analgesia condition, where there was dull sensation. The third type was anaesthesia condition where there was no sensation.

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria are

- The 120 patients those who were involved in the study should be between 20-60 years of age.
- The patient who had an incident of orthopedic surgery in the upper limb, which is done with supraclavicular Brachial Plexus block.
- The patient who were available for follow-up.
- The patient from whom the required information or data could be collected.

Exclusion Criteria

There are specific criteria based on which patients are excluded from the study includes,

- Verbal and written consent should be taken from each of the patients before selection.
- The patient who were transferred to other facilities for some reasons.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS (Statistical Package For Social Sciences) 15.0 version is a software utilized for statistical analysis is used here in the study. All the values were denoted as % and mean±standard deviation (SD). Intra group and inter group comparison and their variation was studied using ANOVA test (Analysis of Variance Test). Any change in the factors used at 2-time spans can be determined using paired 't' test. Apart from the said ones, various other tests were also included for the analysis and determination of different parameters, which are Chi-square test, Kruskal Wallis H test and Mann Whitey U test.

Result

Figure 1 shows a detailed comparison of the sensory and motor responses among three groups. Group I shows a sensory response mean of 10.85 with a standard deviation of 3.05, while the motor response mean is 21.83 with a standard deviation of 4.55. In Group II, the sensory response mean is 10 with a standard deviation of 2.12, and the motor response mean is 15.14 with a standard deviation of 4.25. Group III exhibits a sensory response mean of 21.25 with a standard deviation of 6.25, and a motor response mean of 28.19 with a standard deviation of 4.45. These values indicate variations in both sensory and motor responses across the three groups,

highlighting differences in the duration and variability of these responses.

Figure 1: Time required for sensory and motor onset in both the group

Table 1 presents a comparison of the duration of sensory and motor block across three different groups. For the sensory block, Group I, consisting of 40 subjects, exhibited a duration range between 250 to 520 minutes, with a mean duration of 370 minutes and a standard deviation of 55.25 minutes. Group II, also with 40 subjects, showed a duration range between 320 to 450 minutes, having a mean duration of 420.65 minutes and a standard deviation of 40.32 minutes, which was statistically significant. Group III, again comprising 40 subjects, had a sensory block duration ranging from 200 to 400 minutes, with a mean of 302.05 minutes and a standard

deviation of 53.21 minutes. The total number of subjects across all groups was 120. For the motor block, Group I's duration ranged from 220 to 410 minutes, with a mean of 320.45 minutes and a standard deviation of 45.21 minutes. Group II had durations ranging from 280 to 430 minutes, with a mean of 356 minutes and a standard deviation of 35.56 minutes. Group III displayed a range from 190 to 350 minutes, with a mean duration of 271.24 minutes and a standard deviation of 65.73 minutes. Again, the total number of subjects was 120. The p-value for the motor block durations was 0.0498, indicating statistical significance.

Table 1: Comparison of the duration of sensory and motor block in both the group

Sensory Block				
Group	No.	Range (min-max)	Mean±SD	P-value
Group I	40	250-520	370±55.25	0.0355
Group II	40	320-450	420.65±40.32*	
Group III	40	200-400	302.05±53.21	
Total	120	200-400		
Motor Block				
Group	No.	Range (min-max)	Mean±SD	P-value
Group I	40	220-410	320.45±45.21	0.0498
Group II	40	280-430	356±35.56	
Group III	40	190-350	271.24±65.73	
Total	120	190-350		

*Significant

Table 2 outlines the time to analgesic dose required among the three groups. Group I, with 40 subjects, had a time range from 330 to 420 minutes, a mean of 380.02 minutes, and a standard deviation of 19.15 minutes, with a p-value of 0.0335, indicating

statistical significance. Group II, also with 40 subjects, showed a range from 550 to 660 minutes, with a mean time of 655.36 minutes and a standard deviation of 20.19 minutes. Group III, with 40 subjects, exhibited a range from 170 to 240 minutes,

a mean of 200.05 minutes, and a standard deviation of 21.23 minutes. The total number of subjects across all groups was 120.

Table 2: Time to analgesic dose required (in minutes) among the groups

Group	No.	Range (min-max)	Mean±SD	P-value
Group I	40	330-420	380.02±19.15	0.0335
Group II	40	550-660	655.36±20.19	
Group III	40	170-240	200.05±21.23	
Total	120	170-240		

Discussion

The superiority of Bupivacaine over contemporary anaesthetic agents like opioids and alternatives like Lidocaine and mepivacaine has made it to WHO's List of Essential Medicines [16]. Apart from the use of Bupivacaine in emergency wound care, its long-duration efficacy has made it particularly useful for lengthy surgical procedures and postoperative pain management. Although Bupivacaine is an effective anaesthetic, in addition to its toxicity issues [17], its slow onset of action, which was reported to be around 8 to 12 minutes for blocks of small nerves, has been of concern [18]. To counteract these limitations, the use of adjuvants can complement Bupivacaine by decreasing the dosage of local anaesthetic and supplementary opioids. Furthermore, adjuvants can lead to quicker onset, more complete anaesthesia, and longer-lasting pain relief. The two commonly investigated adjuvants are Tramadol and Dexamethasone. Tramadol that acts as an opioid agonist with serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor (SNRI) capabilities has been shown to enhance the analgesic effects of local anaesthetics when used as an adjuvant [7]. Dexamethasone, a synthetic glucocorticoid, is believed to have a membrane-stabilizing impact and a local anaesthetic-like action, which can extend the period of the nerve block [12].

The effectiveness of Tramadol and Dexamethasone as adjuvants to Bupivacaine especially in brachial plexus blocks has been extensively studied in the literature. Most of those studies have aimed to compare the onset and extent of sensory and motor inhibition, the duration of postoperative pain management, and the incidence of adverse effects between the two adjuvants [19]. In a prospective, double-blind, randomized study that explored the efficacy of Tramadol and Dexamethasone as adjuvants to Bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks. They found that the time of painlessness was significantly extended in the dexamethasone group (1023.87 ± 161.01 minutes) in comparison to the Tramadol group (454.47 ± 44.29 minutes), indicating that Dexamethasone was better than Tramadol in prolonging postoperative pain management [20]. Similarly, Nagar et al. performed a comparative study between Tramadol and Dexamethasone as adjuvants to Bupivacaine in

supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks. They reported that the onset of sensory and motor blockade was quicker, and the extent of sensory and motor inhibition was extensive in the dexamethasone group compared to the Tramadol group. The time to initial rescue pain relief was also considerably longer in the dexamethasone group [6]. In support of previous studies, Apte et al. also found that the duration of analgesia was significantly longer in the dexamethasone group compared to the Tramadol group when used as adjuvants to Bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks. They determined that Dexamethasone with local anaesthetic persists postoperative analgesia substantially more than Tramadol [21]. Girgis et al. also investigated the effect of adding Dexamethasone to Bupivacaine in caudal anaesthesia in pediatric patients. They reported that the duration of postoperative analgesia was significantly prolonged in the dexamethasone-bupivacaine group compared to the bupivacaine-only group [22]. Similarly, a study by Shrestha et al. reported that combining Dexamethasone with local anaesthetic significantly extends postoperative pain relief compared to Tramadol (P<0.05) when administered with local anaesthesia in brachial plexus block for upper extremity surgery [23]. These studies evidently demonstrate that the use of both Tramadol and Dexamethasone as adjuvants to Bupivacaine can significantly prolong the period of analgesia compared to Bupivacaine without any adjuvant. However, there is an ample amount of evidence that suggests the superiority of Dexamethasone over Tramadol in this regard. The improved analgesic effects with adjuvants can benefit anaesthesia practice by providing more effective pain control, facilitating faster recovery, and reducing opioid consumption for patient's surgeries.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Dexamethasone has shown better outcome than Tramadol. Dexamethasone exhibited significantly better sensory and motor responses, as well as more favorable durations for sensory and motor blocks. The time required for an analgesic dose in Dexamethasone was also superior, indicating a prolonged effect and reduced necessity for additional medication. This

study provides significant clinical insights into managing sensory and motor responses and optimizing analgesic protocols. The findings indicate that Dexamethasone markedly enhances both sensory and motor response efficacy, leading to better patient outcomes compared to tramadol. The prolonged sensory and motor block durations with Dexamethasone suggest a more efficient approach to pain and motor function management. Additionally, the reduced frequency of analgesic doses required with Dexamethasone highlights improved patient comfort and decreased reliance on medication. These results support the adoption of Dexamethasone in relevant medical procedures, promoting more effective pain management strategies and enhanced patient care protocols.

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